

Some Thiocyanato Complexes of Cadmium(II) with Substituted Pyridines and Imidazoles

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The complexes formed by cadmium(II) thiocyanate with 3-acetyl-, 3-bromo-, 3-methyl-, 4-acetyl-, 4-cyano-, 4-benzoyl pyridines, isoquinoline, 3,5-lutidine and imidazole, 2-methyl imidazole, 2-methyl benzimidazoles have been characterised through elemental analysis and molar conductance data. On the basis of infra-red spectroscopic studies, probable structures are discussed.

THE versatile thiocyanate group offers interesting bonding possibilities¹. In metal ion complexes, it may coordinate through either nitrogen (M-NCS), sulphur (M-SCN) or both (M-SCN-M) and examples of complexes containing each type of thiocyanate bonding are known. Also there are examples where it involves isomerism. There is a great deal of interest in the study of linkage isomerism of pseudo-halides in the coordination compounds where the thiocyanate ion is considered to be the best potential ligand. The studies with this ligand have shown that various factors like the effect of other ligands including their basicities and steric hindrance, π bonding and preparative conditions are responsible for the mode of bonding of this ion to the metal. The i.r. spectral features of some complexes of zinc(II) thiocyanate with different nitrogen donor ligands have been studied by Nelson & Shepherd² and Clark & Williams³. However no work seems to have been reported on the complexes of cadmium(II) thiocyanate with the ligands listed above. We now report the preparation and i. r. spectral studies of the complexes formed by cadmium(II) thiocyanate with some neutral monodentate nitrogen donor ligands.

Experimental

To an ethanolic solution of cadmium chloride was added excess of ethanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate. The precipitated potassium chloride was filtered off. The filtrate containing cadmium thiocyanate was treated with excess of the ligand and was shaken thoroughly. Some complexes separated out either immediately or after some time whereas some required refluxing for half an hour and standing overnight. For preparing complexes with imidazoles, aqueous solutions of cadmium nitrate, ammonium thiocyanate and the respective imidazole were mixed in stoichiometric ratio and vigorously stirred. All the compounds were suction filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Stoichiometry of these complexes was established by metal and thiocyanate analyses following standard methods. Electrolytic conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature in $\sim 10^{-3}$ solutions in pyridine and acetone using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge type CL 010¹ and a dip type cell. I.R. spectra in the range 5000-650 cm^{-1} were recorded on Nujol mulls using SP 200 double-beam spectrophotometer with rock salt optics.

Analyses, melting point, conductivity and infra-red spectral data are recorded in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds reported are diamagnetic as expected for a completely filled 4 d^{10} non-bonding shell of cadmium(II). The molar conductance data of the complexes in pyridine and acetone are very low indicating that they are essentially non-electrolytes. Slightly higher values for Δ_M in acetone ranging between 27 and 38 mhos in case of imidazole complexes may be due to partial dissociation in solution; the Δ_M for 1 : 1 electrolytes being round about 150 mhos.

As is evident from Table 1, cadmium(II) thiocyanate formed 1 : 2 complexes with all the ligands except 4-benzoyl pyridine, isoquinoline and 3,5-lutidine which gave 1 : 4 complexes. Partial i.r. spectral data and their assignment for these complexes are listed in Table 2. Cadmium(II), being d^{10} ion, does not show d-d transition and therefore stereochemistry of its complexes cannot be derived from electronic spectra. Information of the structures of the complexes in the present studies has been derived from their i.r. spectral measurements.

In the i.r. spectra of the metal complexes containing coordinated thiocyanate groups, certain correlations between ν_{CN} and ν_{CS} modes and the

TABLE 1—MELTING POINT, ANALYSIS AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE THIOCYANATO COMPLEXES OF CADMIUM(II)

Compound	Colour and Form	M.P. (°C)	%Cadmium		%Thiocyanate		Λ_m (mhos) (Pyridine/Acetone)
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{3-ac-py})_2$	Brown crystalline	160	23.2	23.9	24.8	24.6	9.0
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{3-br-py})_2$	Pale yellow crystalline	175	20.2	20.6	21.1	21.3	4.7
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{3-me-py})_2$	White crystalline	148	26.8	27.1	27.7	27.9	4.3
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{4-cy-py})_2$	White crystalline	220	25.3	25.5	26.3	26.5	4.5
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{4-ac-py})_2$	Brown crystalline	205	23.1	23.9	24.1	24.6	7.0
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{Iq})_4$	White crystalline	110	14.9	15.1	15.3	15.5	9.0
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{3,5-lut})_4$	White crystalline	190	17.0	17.1	17.1	17.6	4.9
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{4-benz-py})_2$	White crystalline	195	11.5	11.6	11.8	12.0	8.0
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{Iz})_2$	White micro crystalline	185	30.7	31.2	31.2	31.5	38
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{2-me-Iz})_2$	Silky crystalline	195	27.9	28.6	28.9	28.5	96
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{2-me-benz-Iz})_2$	White crystalline (needle-shaped)	140	19.9	20.6	21.8	21.3	27

TABLE 2—INFRA-RED SPECTRAL DATA OF CADMIUM(II) THIOCYANATE COMPLEXES

Compound	Thiocyanate		Substituted pyridines	
	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{3-ac-py})_2$	2088(v.s)	758(s)	1689(w), 1588(s)	
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{3-br-py})_2$	2100(v.s)	769(s)	1589(s), 1553(w), 1521(w)	
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{3-me-py})_2$	2095(v.s)	765(s)	1603(s), 1583(s)	
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{4-cy-py})_2$	2090(v.s)	764(s)	1603(v.s), 1548(s)	
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{4-ac-py})_2$	2122(v.s)	734(s)	1703(s), 1621(w), 1564(m)	
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{Iq})_4$	2050(v.s)	820(s)	1623(v.s), 1591(s), 1501(w)	
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{3,5-lut})_4$	2060(v.s)	802(s)	1603(s)	
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{4-benz-py})_2$	{2060(v.s) {2110(w)	800(s)	1663(v.s), 1603(s), 1553(s)	
			Imidazoles	
			$\delta(\text{N}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{Iz})_2$	2110(v.s)	752(m)	1423(m)	3350(m)
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{2-me-Iz})_2$	{2145(s) {2080(v.s)	758(s)	1440(sh)	3270(m)
$\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{2-me-benz-Iz})_2$	{2120(s) {2080(v.s)	738(v.s)	1413(sh)	3360(m)

v.s.=very sharp ; s=sharp ; m=medium ; w=weak ; sh=shoulder.

type of thiocyanate bonding have been made¹⁻⁶. For the M-NCS bonding, ν_{CN} and ν_{CS} appear to fall in the range $\sim 2080-2040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $860-780 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The corresponding ranges for M-SCN bonding are $\sim 2120-2080 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $720-680 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. For bridging thiocyanate groups M-SCN-M, ν_{CN} falls in a broader and generally higher range than M-NCS while ν_{CS} usually occurs at intermediate frequencies. In the ionic thiocyanate, ν_{CN} occurs at $\sim 1963 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and ν_{CS} falls at $\sim 963 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Moreover the mode of thiocyanate bonding may also be characterised by examining the doubly degenerate δ_{NCS} frequency.

In the i.r. spectra of 1:2 complexes of cadmium(II), the ν_{CN} occurs at $2088-2145 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the ν_{CS} at $734-765 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicative of a bridging thiocyanate group. The δ_{NCS} could not be recorded due to the limitation of the range of the instrument used. The observed frequencies of ν_{CN} and ν_{CS}

modes in these complexes are in excellent agreement with similar modes in $\text{ML}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ complexes (where M=Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and L=monodentate ligand) which are shown by X-ray crystallography and i.r. spectral measurements to have bridging thiocyanate groups^{2,8}. The relative affinities of ligand atoms for different metal ions have been studied by Chatt et al⁹. Accordingly zinc(II) and mercury(II) form M-NCS and M-SCN bonded complexes respectively. Cadmium(II) is intermediate in character and forms both Cd-NCS and Cd-SCN bonds⁹. Several cadmium(II) halide complexes, CdL_2X_2 (L=monodentate ligand and X=Cl, Br, I) were reported earlier and their stereochemistry was established¹⁰⁻¹². Although their empirical formulae suggested 4-coordination round the metal ion, they were mostly 6-coordinate polymeric structures built from chains of octahedra with halogen bridges. Thus, polymerisation through halogen or thiocyanate bridging is common in

cadmium complexes and hence the presence of thiocyanate bridges may be expected in the reported 1:2 cadmium(II) complexes having the formula $CdL_2(SCN)_2$ as evidenced by i.r. spectra. This thiocyanate bridging increases the apparent coordination and results in polymeric octahedral structures with adjacent metal atoms linked by two $-SCN-$ bridges to form quasiplanar eight-membered ring $-Cd(SCN)_2Cd-$. The 1:4 complexes of Cd(II) having the formula $CdL_4(NCS)_2$ where L is isoquinoline, 3,5-lutidine and 4-benzoyl pyridine are of monomeric octahedral form with terminal N-bonded thiocyanate group as is evidenced by the i.r. spectral data.

The $\nu(C\cdots C) + \nu(C\cdots N)$ bands due to substituted pyridines obtained round about 1600 cm^{-1} and 1550 cm^{-1} in the i.r. spectra of the complexes indicate that these ligands are bonded through the nitrogen atom as suggested by Das & Ramana Rao¹³. In the i.r. spectra of imidazole complexes, the (N-H) bending and stretching frequencies which occur at round about 1400 and 3300 cm^{-1} respectively clearly indicate that the imidazole and its derivatives are coordinated through the tertiary nitrogen atom as confirmed by X-ray structural studies earlier¹⁴.

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References

1. J. L. BURMEISTER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 205; 1968, **3**, 225.
2. S. M. NELSON and T. M. SHEPHERD, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2125.
3. R. J. H. CLARK and C. M. WILLIAMS, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1966, **22**, 1081.
4. K. NAKAMOTO, *Infra-red Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds*. John Wiley, New York, 1970.
5. J. L. BURMEISTER and F. BASOLO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 1587.
6. I. S. AHUJA and A. GARG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 1929.
7. M. A. PORAI-KOSHITS and G. N. TISCHEHENENKO, *Kristallografiya*, 1959, **4**, 239.
8. S. AHLAND, J. CHATT and N. R. DAVIES, *Quart. Rev. Chem. Soc. London*, 1958, **12**, 265.
9. A. TRAMER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **59**, 232.
10. G. E. COATES and D. RID LEY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 166.
11. J. R. ALLAN, D. H. BROWN, R. H. NUTTALL and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Chem. Soc. A.*, 1966, 1031.
12. I. S. AHUJA, D. H. BROWN, R. H. NUTTALL and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 1105.
13. A. K. DAS and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 823.
14. B. K. S. LUNDBERG, *Acta. Crystallogr.*, 1966, **21**, 901.